

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

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GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SHORT STORY AS A LITERARY GENRE

Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada qisqa hikoya adabiy janri sifatidagi umumiy xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada qisqa hikoyaning asosiy belgilari, jumladan, qisqalik, syujetning yaxlitligi, cheklangan sonli qahramonlar va bitta voqea yoki ziddiyatga e`tibor qaratilishi ko`rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, janrning strukturaviy va uslubiy jihatlari, ya`ni hikoya qilish texnikasi, xarakterlar tasviri, makon va mavzu tahlil qilinadi. Maxsus e`tibor qisqa hikoyaning badiiy va estetik funksiyalari, shuningdek, ijtimoiy, psixologik va madaniy haqiqatlarni aks ettirishdagi o`rniga qaratiladi. Maqola qisqa hikoyaning zamonaviy va jahon adabiyotidagi ahamiyatini yoritadi.

Annotation:

This article examines the general characteristics of the short story as a literary genre. It analyzes the defining features of the short story, including brevity, unity of plot, limited number of characters, and concentration on a single event or conflict. The article also explores the structural and stylistic elements of the genre, such as narrative technique, characterization, setting, and theme. Special attention is paid to the artistic and aesthetic functions of the short story, as well as its role in reflecting social, psychological, and cultural realities. The study highlights the significance of the short story in the development of world literature.

Аннотация:

В данной статье анализируются общие характеристики короткого рассказа как литературного жанра. Рассматриваются основные признаки короткого рассказа, включая краткость, целостность сюжета, ограниченное число персонажей и сосредоточенность на одном событии или конфликте. Также исследуются структурные и стилистические особенности жанра, такие как техника повествования, характеристика персонажей, пространство и тема. Особое внимание уделяется художественным и эстетическим функциям короткого рассказа, а также его роли в отражении социальных, психологических и культурных реалий. Статья подчеркивает значение короткого рассказа в современной и мировой литературе.

Kalit so`zlar: *qisqa hikoya, adabiy janr, hikoya tuzilmasi, syujet, xarakterizatsiya, mavzu, qisqalik, badiiy xususiyatlar, adabiy tahlil, jahon adabiyoti.*

Key words: *short story, literary genre, narrative structure, plot, characterization, theme, brevity, artistic features, literary analysis, world literature.*

Ключевые слова: *короткий рассказ, литературный жанр, структура повествования, сюжет, характеристика персонажей, тема, краткость, художественные особенности, литературный анализ, мировая литература.*

INTRODUCTION

A short story is a piece of prose fiction, which can be read in a single sitting. Emerging from earlier oral storytelling traditions in the 17th century, the short story has grown to encompass a body of work so diverse as to defy easy characterization¹. At its most prototypical the short story features a small cast of named characters, and focuses on a self-contained incident with the intent of evoking a "single effect" or mood.² In doing so, short stories make use of plot, resonance, and other dynamic components to a far greater degree than is typical of an anecdote, yet to a far lesser degree than a novel. While the short story is largely distinct from the novel, authors of both generally draw from a common pool of literary techniques.

Short stories have no set length. In terms of word count there is no official demarcation between

an anecdote, a short story, and a novel. Rather, the form's parameters are given by the rhetorical and practical context in which a given story is produced and considered, so that what constitutes a short story may differ between genres, countries, eras, and commentators. Like the novel, the short story's predominant shape reflects the demands of the available markets for publication, and the evolution of the form seems closely tied to the evolution of the publishing industry and the submission guidelines of its constituent houses.

The short story has been considered both an apprenticeship form preceding more lengthy works, and a crafted form in its own right, collected together in books of similar length, price, and distribution as novels. Short story writers may define their works as part of the artistic and personal expression of the form. They

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Short_story

² Poe, Edgar Allan (1984). *Edgar Allan Poe: Essays and Reviews*. Library of America. pp. 569–77.

may also attempt to resist categorization by genre and fixed formation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Determining what exactly separates a short story from longer fictional formats is problematic. A classic definition of a short story is that one should be able to read it in one sitting, a point most notably made in Edgar Allan Poe's essay "Thomas Le Moineau (Le Moile)" (1846). Interpreting this standard nowadays is problematic, since the expected length of "one sitting" may now be briefer than it was in Poe's era. Other definitions place the maximum word count of the short story at anywhere from 1,000 to 4,000. In contemporary usage, the term short story most often refers to a work of fiction no shorter than 1,000 and no longer than 20,000 words. Stories of fewer than 1,000 words are sometimes referred to as "short short stories",³ or "flash fiction."

As a point of reference for the genre writer, the Science Fiction and Fantasy Writers of America define short story length in the Nebula Awards for science fiction submission guidelines as having a word count of fewer than 7,500.

Longer stories that cannot be called novels are sometimes considered "novellas" or novelettes and, like short stories, may be collected into the more marketable form of "collections", often containing previously unpublished stories. Sometimes, authors who do not have the time or money to write a novella or novel decide to write short stories instead, working out a deal with a popular website or magazine to publish them for profit.

As a concentrated form of narrative prose fiction, the short story has been theorised through the traditional elements of dramatic structure: exposition (the introduction of setting, situation and main characters), complication (the event that introduces the conflict), rising action, crisis (the decisive moment for the protagonist and his commitment to a course of action), climax (the point of highest interest in terms of the conflict and the point with the most action) and resolution (the point when the conflict is resolved). Because of their length, short stories may or may not follow this pattern. For example, modern short stories only occasionally have an exposition, more typically beginning in the middle of the action (*in medias res*). As with longer stories, plots of short stories also have a climax, crisis, or turning point. However, the endings of many short stories are abrupt and open and may or may not have a moral or practical lesson. As with any art form, the exact characteristics of a short story will vary by creator. Short stories tend to be less complex than novels. Usually a short story focuses on one incident; has a single plot, a single setting, and a small number of characters; and covers a short period of time. The modern short story form emerged from oral story-telling traditions, the brief moralistic narratives of parables and fables, and the prose anecdote, all of

these being forms of a swiftly sketched situation that quickly comes to its point. With the rise of the realistic novel, the short story evolved in a parallel tradition, with some of its first distinctive examples in the tales of E. T. A. Hoffmann.

RESULTS AND ANALYSYS

The character of the form developed particularly with authors known for their short fiction, either by choice (they wrote nothing else) or by critical regard, which acknowledged the focus and craft required in the short form. An example is Jorge Luis Borges, who won American fame with "The Garden of Forking Paths", published in the August 1948 Ellery Queen's Mystery Magazine. Another example is O. Henry (author of "Gift of the Magi"), for whom the O. Henry Award is named. Other of his most popular, inventive and most often reprinted stories (among over 600) include: A Municipal Report, An Unfinished Story, A Blackjack Barginer, A Lickpenny Lover, Mammon and the Archer, Two Thanksgiving Day Gentlemen, The Last Leaf. American examples include: Jack London, Ambrose Bierce, F. Scott Fitzgerald, Ernest Hemingway, William Faulkner, Flannery O'Connor, John Cheever, and Raymond Carver. Science fiction short story with a special poetic touch was a genre developed with great popular success by Ray Bradbury. The genre of the short story was often neglected until the second half of the 19th century. The evolution of printing technologies and periodical editions were among the factors contributing to the increasing importance of short story publications. Among others, pioneering role in founding the rules of the genre in the Western canon have: Rudyard Kipling (United Kingdom), Anton Chekhov (Russia), Guy de Maupassant (France), Manuel Gutiérrez Nájera (Mexico) and Rubén Darío (Nicaragua). An important theoretical example for storytelling analysis is provided by Walter Benjamin in his illuminated essay The Storytelle where he argues about the decline of storytelling art and the incommunicability of experiences in the modern world⁴. Oscar Wilde's essay The Decay of Lying and Henry James's The Art of Fiction are also partly related with this subject.

Short stories date back to oral storytelling traditions which originally produced epics such as Homer's Iliad and Odyssey. Oral narratives were often told in the form of rhyming orrrhythmic verse, often including recurring sections or, in the case of Homer, Homeric epithets. Such stylistic devices often acted as mnemonics for easier recall, rendition and adaptation of the story. Short sections of verse might focus on individual narratives that could be told at one sitting. The overall arc of the tale would emerge only through the telling of multiple such sections.

CONCLUSION

In Europe, the oral story-telling tradition began to develop into written stories in the early 14th century, most notably with Geoffrey Chaucer's Canterbury Tales and Giovanni Boccaccio's Decameron. Both of these books are composed of individual short stories

³ Deirdre Fulton (2008-06-11). "Who reads short shorts?". thePhoneix.com. Retrieved 2013-06-06. *each of their (less-than-1000-word) stories*

⁴ Short Story in Jacob E. Safra e.a., The New Encyclopædia Britannica, 15th edition, Micropaedia volume 10, Chicago, 1998.

(which range from farce or humorous anecdotes to well-crafted literary fictions) set within a larger narrative story (a frame story), although the frame-tale device was not adopted by all writers. At the end of the 16th century, some of the most popular short stories in Europe were the darkly tragic "novella" of Matteo Bandello (especially in their French translation).

The mid-17th century in France saw the development of a refined short novel, the "nouvelle", by such authors as Madame de Lafayette. In the 1690s, traditional fairy tales began to be published (one of the most famous collections was by Charles Perrault). The appearance of Antoine Galland's first modern translation of the Thousand and One Nights (or Arabian Nights)

(from 1704; another translation appeared in 1710–12) would have an enormous influence on the 18th-century European short stories of Voltaire, Diderot and others.

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